

Exploring Noncommutative Polynomial Equation Methods for Discrete-Time Quaternionic Control*

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Abstract—We present new polynomial-based methods for SISO discrete-time quaternionic systems, highlighting how noncommutative multiplication modifies classical control approaches. Defining quaternionic polynomials via a backward-shift operator, we examine left and right fraction representations of transfer functions, showing that right zeros correspond to similarity classes of quaternionic matrix right eigenvalues. We then propose a feedback design procedure that generalizes pole placement to quaternions—a first approach using a genuine quaternionic polynomial equation. An illustrative example demonstrates its effectiveness.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quaternions and quaternionic systems are gaining importance across science and engineering—especially in computer graphics, robotics, and control—because they effectively represent orientations and rotations [5], [7]. While many control systems papers treat quaternions as real-number vectors, here we view them as an extension of the complex numbers called hypercomplex numbers.

Owing to their noncommutative multiplication, quaternionic SISO systems differ from classical real or complex SISO systems. In some ways, they resemble MIMO systems, but they also exhibit unique behaviors that complicate design, rendering many classical tools inapplicable. This underscores the need for alternative methods of control analysis and design. Our approach offers the first method that utilizes a genuine quaternionic polynomial equation.

II. BACKGROUND MATHEMATICS

A quaternion has the form $a + b\mathbf{i} + c\mathbf{j} + d\mathbf{k}$, where a, b, c, d are real numbers, and $\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}$ are imaginary units. Quaternions generalize the complex numbers but feature *noncommutative multiplication* (e.g., $\mathbf{ij} = \mathbf{k}$ but $\mathbf{ji} = -\mathbf{k}$).

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Their skew field is denoted by \mathbb{H} . Quaternions p, q are *similar* if there exists a quaternion u such that $p = uqu^{-1}$, forming a *similarity class* $[q]$.

Quaternionic matrices also differ from their complex counterparts. For instance, they lack a determinant, and *left eigenvalues* $Av = \lambda v$ differ from *right eigenvalues* $Av = v\lambda$. For computational algorithms, see [9] and references therein.

A *discrete-time quaternionic signal* is an infinite sequence $x = \{x_n, x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}, \dots\}$, $x_k \in \mathbb{H}, n \in \mathbb{Z}$. Using the backward-shift operator d , defined as a sequence of zeros except for one at $n = 1$, any signal can be expressed as a formal series $x = x_n d^n + x_{n+1} d^{n+1} + \dots$ (see [3]). A sequence is *causal* if it starts at $n = 0$ and *strictly causal*, if it starts at $n > 0$. A causal sequence is *stable* if it converges to zero.

A *quaternionic polynomial* is a causal sequence with finitely many nonzero terms

$$a_m d^m + a_{m+1} d^{m+1} + \dots + a_n d^n, a_i \in \mathbb{H}. \quad (1)$$

Here, the *indeterminate* d commutes with the coefficients a_i , and basic properties such as degree and order follow standard polynomial definitions.

However, due to noncommutativity, division, divisors, and greatest common divisors depend on the side of multiplication. Similarly, evaluation is noncommutative. A quaternion q is a *right zero* of the polynomial $a(d) \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ if $a_0 + a_1 q + \dots + a_n q^n = 0$ and a *left zero* if $a_0 + q a_1 + \dots + q^n a_n = 0$. A quaternionic polynomial of degree n has either n or infinitely many right zeros [2], [4]. Two polynomials $a, b \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ are right-zero coprime if they share no common right zero.

A polynomial $a \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ is *stable* if its inverse a^{-1} is a stable quaternionic sequence. This requires that all right zeros of a have norms greater than 1, a direct consequence of using the backward-shift operator d instead of the forward-shift z .

Fractions of real polynomials are a standard tool in control theory. However, quaternionic polynomial

fractions behave more like fractions of real polynomial matrices due to the noncommutativity of multiplication. This requires distinguishing between left and right fractions: A *left quaternionic polynomial fraction* is

$$a_\ell^{-1}b_\ell, \quad a_\ell, b_\ell \in \mathbb{H}[d], \quad (2)$$

where a_ℓ is the *left denominator* and b_ℓ is the *left numerator*. A *right quaternionic polynomial fraction* is

$$a_r b_r^{-1}, \quad a_r, b_r \in \mathbb{H}[d], \quad (3)$$

where a_r is the *right numerator* and b_r is the *right denominator*. Typically, the polynomials in (3) must be right coprime, and those in (2) left coprime.

We use the backward-shift *indeterminate* (operator) d instead of the quaternionic *variable* z^{-1} to avoid non-commutativity issues and as the quaternionic z -transform is not yet fully developed.

III. QUATERNIONIC SYSTEMS

State-space models for discrete-time single-input, single-output systems over quaternions are commonly expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} x(k+1) &= Fx(k) + Gu(k), \\ y(k) &= Hx(k) + Ju(k), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where, all signals $(u(k), y(k) \in \mathbb{H}, x(k) \in \mathbb{H}^n)$ and matrices $(F \in \mathbb{H}^{n \times n}, G \in \mathbb{H}^{n \times m}, H \in \mathbb{H}^{l \times n}, J \in \mathbb{H}^{l \times m})$ have quaternion entries.

The causal scalar quaternionic sequence

$$S = S_0 + S_1 d + S_2 d^2 + \dots, \quad (5)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} S_0 &= J, \\ S_k &= HF^{k-1}G, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

serves as the system's transfer function. It can also be expressed compactly as

$$S = J + dH(I_n - dF)^{-1}G. \quad (7)$$

Any quaternionic transfer function can be represented as a quaternionic polynomial fraction

$$S = p_\ell^{-1}q_\ell = q_r p_r^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

where p_ℓ, q_ℓ are left coprime and p_r, q_r are right coprime. These fractions are unique up to multiplication by a nonzero quaternion from within.

The inverse matrix $(I_n - dF)^{-1}$ in (7) is not a quaternionic polynomial, making its computation intricate.

However, we can avoid this by expressing S in (7) as a polynomial fraction from. Below, we outline the procedure for obtaining the left fraction.

Algorithm 1.

Given: F, G, H, J .

1) Find $p_\ell \in \mathbb{H}[d], Q_\ell \in \mathbb{H}^{1 \times n}[d]$ such that

$$p_\ell^{-1}Q_\ell = dH(I_n - dF)^{-1}.$$

2) Compute the numerator

$$q_\ell = p_\ell J + Q_\ell G \in \mathbb{H}[d].$$

Result: $p_\ell, q_\ell \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ satisfying $S = p_\ell^{-1}(d)q_\ell(d)$.

By ensuring coprimeness at each step, the resulting p_ℓ, q_ℓ remains left coprime. Similarly, the right polynomial fraction representation of S can be directly obtained.

Finally, the right fraction $q_r p_r^{-1}$ follows from the left fraction $p_\ell^{-1}q_\ell$ by computing the right null space of the matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} p_\ell & -q_\ell \end{bmatrix}.$$

A realization (E, F, G, H) is minimal if it has the fewest states among all that realize S . Only such a minimal realization uniquely corresponds to S ; nonminimal ones harbor hidden (unreachable or unobservable) modes. If the realization is minimal and fractions coprime, we have

$$n = \max(\deg p_\ell, \deg q_\ell) = \max(\deg p_r, \deg q_r),$$

since we operate in the backward-shift d .

In classical systems, if the realization is minimal and the fractions in (8) are coprime, then all three polynomials $\det(I_n - dF)$, p_ℓ and p_r share the same zeros, which also coincide with the reciprocals of the eigenvalues of F . However, in quaternionic systems, the usual notions of determinant and characteristic polynomial do not directly apply. Nevertheless, as we will show, although the right zeros of p_ℓ and p_r may differ, they remain similar—and they are also similar to the reciprocals of the right eigenvalues of F .

Theorem 1. Let $p_\ell, q_\ell \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ be left coprime and $p_r, q_r \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ be right coprime polynomials such that

$$p_\ell^{-1}q_\ell = q_r p_r^{-1}.$$

Then, for every right zero r_{p_ℓ} of p_ℓ , there exists a right zero r_{p_r} of p_r such that

$$r_{p_r} \in [r_{p_\ell}].$$

Conversely, for every right zero r_{p_r} of p_r there exists a right zero r_{p_ℓ} of p_ℓ such that

$$r_{p_\ell} \in [r_{p_r}].$$

Proof. Since the polynomial fractions are equal, we have

$$p_\ell q_r = q_\ell p_r. \quad (9)$$

The zeros of p_ℓ are similar (though not necessarily equal) to the zeros of the left-hand side of this equation and, thus, similar to those of the right-hand side. Given that $p_\ell, q_\ell \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ are left coprime, the zeros of p_ℓ must be similar to the zeros of p_r . The reverse direction follows by an analogous argument. \square

The reverse process—finding a state realization for a given transfer function—is more complex for quaternionic systems than for classical ones. Despite their structural similarity, quaternionic realizations require additional steps.

Theorem 2 (Quaternionic state realization). Let S be a quaternionic transfer function expressed as a left quaternionic polynomial fraction

$$S = a_\ell^{-1} b_\ell = (1 + a_1 d + \dots + a_n d^n)^{-1} (b_0 + \dots + b_n d^n),$$

where $a_0 = a_\ell(0) = 1$. Then, a corresponding state-space realization (E, F, G, J) satisfying (7) is given by

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \\ -\hat{a}_n & -\hat{a}_{n-1} & \hat{a}_{n-2} & \dots & -\hat{a}_1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad G = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$H = [\hat{b}_n, \hat{b}_{n-1}, \dots, \hat{b}_1], \quad J = [b_0].$$

Here, \hat{a}_i are the coefficients of the polynomial $\hat{a} \in \mathbb{H}[d]$, obtained from the left-to-right fraction conversion

$$\hat{b}(d) \hat{a}(d)^{-1} = a(d)^{-1} \tilde{b}(d), \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{a}_0 = 1$ and $\tilde{b}(d) \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ is given by

$$\tilde{b}(d) = \tilde{b}_1 d + \dots + \tilde{b}_n d^n = b_\ell(d) - b_0 a_\ell(d). \quad (11)$$

Proof. The proof follows the classical system approach but requires additional polynomial fraction conversions and technical details. Due to space constraints, we omit these here. \square

This realization corresponds to the quaternionic counterpart of the classical controllable canonical form.

While the equations may resemble those in classical systems, they integrate coefficients from multiple polynomial fractions.

Theorem 3. If r_i is a right zero of the denominator polynomial a_ℓ , then

$$r_i^{-1} \in [\lambda_{r,i}],$$

where $\lambda_{r,i}$ is some right eigenvalue of F , for $i = 1, \dots, \deg a_\ell$. Moreover, if $\deg b_\ell - \deg a_\ell = k > 0$, then F has additional k additional zero left (and hence also right) eigenvalues.

Proof. First, note that all $r_i \neq 0$ as $a_0 = a_\ell(0) = 1$. By Theorem 1, each r_i is similar to a right zero \hat{r}_i of a_r .

Since F is in a bottom companion form, if a_ℓ were a polynomial in the forward shift z , then its right zeros would correspond to left eigenvalues of F (see [8]). However, since a_ℓ is expressed in the backward shift $d = z^{-1}$, each of its right zeros is the reciprocal of a left eigenvalue of F . By [8], each left eigenvalue of the companion matrix represents an entire class of right eigenvalues, confirming the first claim.

For the second claim, note that since the polynomial fractions are coprime, their denominators share the same degree. If $\hat{a}_n = \hat{a}_{n-1} = \dots = \hat{a}_{n-k} = 0$, the F has k left eigenvalues equal to zero, which implies it also has k right eigenvalues equal to zero. \square

IV. STABILITY

Stability is a fundamental property of linear systems. A system (F, G, H, J) defined by (4) is (internally, asymptotically) stable if, for any initial state $x_0 \in \mathbb{H}^n$, the initial state response

$$S_{x_0} = \{x_0, Fx_0, F^2x_0, \dots\}$$

converges to zero. Similar to (7), this response can be expressed as a left polynomial matrix fraction

$$S_{x_0} = (I_n - dF)^{-1} x_0. \quad (12)$$

Clearly, S_{x_0} converges to zero for any x_0 if and only if the sequence $(I_n - dF)^{-1} = \{I_n, F, F^2, \dots\}$ converges to zero. It is well known that this occurs if and only if all right eigenvalues of the quaternionic matrix F satisfy

$$|\lambda_{r,i}| > 0.$$

If $(I_n - dF)^{-1}$ converges to zero, then the transfer function $S = H(I_n - dF)^{-1} G$ converges to zero. The

converse holds if and only if the system has no unstable hidden modes.

In the polynomial fraction representation

$$S = p_\ell^{-1}q_\ell = q_r p_r^{-1} = J + dH(I_n - dF)^{-1}G, \quad (13)$$

the right zeros of the denominator polynomials p_ℓ and p_r are similar but not necessarily equal to the right eigenvalues of F . Fortunately, this difference does not affect stability analysis.

Theorem 4. Let the realization (F, G, H, D) be minimal, and assume the polynomial fractions in (13) are coprime. Then, all right eigenvalues of F are stable if and only if the denominators p_ℓ and p_r are stable polynomials.

Proof. The proof follows from Proposition 1, noting that all quaternions in a similarity class share the same norm. \square

Proposition 1.

$$|\lambda| > 1, q \in \mathbb{H} \Rightarrow |\mu| > 1, \forall \mu \in [\lambda], \mu \in \mathbb{H}.$$

Proof. This is straightforward, as all quaternions within a similarity class share the same norm (see also [6]). \square

V. FEEDBACK SYSTEM

Consider the output feedback system

$$y = Su + w \quad \text{and} \quad u = -Ry + v, \quad (14)$$

where S is the plant's transfer function, R is the controller's transfer function, u, y are the plant input and output sequences. The external inputs v and w represent responses to initial conditions, external disturbances, etc. As in classical systems (see [3]), the closed-loop transfer functions from v and w to y is given by

$$y = (1 + SR)^{-1}Sv + (1 + SR)^{-1}w. \quad (15)$$

Expressing the plant and controller transfer functions as polynomial fractions

$$S = a_\ell^{-1}b_\ell, \quad R = q_r p_r^{-1}, \quad (16)$$

where $a_\ell, b_\ell, q_r p_r \in \mathbb{H}[d]$, relation (15) transforms into:

$$y = p_r (a_\ell p_r + b_\ell q_r)^{-1} b_\ell v + p_r (a_\ell p_r + b_\ell q_r)^{-1} a_\ell w. \quad (17)$$

Defining the feedback denominator polynomial

$$c = a_\ell p_r + b_\ell q_r \in \mathbb{H}[d], \quad (18)$$

we rewrite (17) as

$$y = p_r c^{-1} b_\ell v + p_r c^{-1} a_\ell w. \quad (19)$$

Converting to left fractions

$$g^{-1}h = p_r c^{-1},$$

and denoting $h_v = hv, h_w = hw$, the closed-loop transfer functions take the form

$$y = g^{-1}h_v v + g^{-1}h_w w. \quad (20)$$

Given a_ℓ, b_ℓ (the plant) and fixing closed-loop denominator polynomial c turns (18) into a linear quaternionic polynomial equation with unknowns p_r and q_r (the controller).

VI. POLYNOMIAL EQUATIONS

Scalar linear polynomial equations are fundamental in classical systems, yet quaternionic polynomials require distinguishing among right-, left-, and two-sided forms due to noncommutative multiplication. For simplicity, we focus on a single form. Specifically, we consider the *quaternionic polynomial equation*

$$a(d)x(d) + b(d)y(d) = c(d), \quad (21)$$

where $a(d), b(d)$ and $c(d)$ are given quaternionic polynomials and $x(d), y(d)$ are unknowns. A solution is any pair $(x(d), y(d))$ from $\mathbb{H}[d]$ that satisfies the equation.

Theorem 5 (Solvability). The equation (21) has a solution if and only if the greatest common left divisor of a and b is also a left divisor of c .

Proof. Let $g = \text{gclid}(a, b)$ so that $a = g\tilde{a}$ and $b = g\tilde{b}$ for some left coprime polynomials $\tilde{a}, \tilde{b} \in \mathbb{H}[d]$. Suppose $x, y \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ is a solution of (21). Substituting $a = g\tilde{a}$ and $b = g\tilde{b}$ into (21) gives

$$g(\tilde{a}x + \tilde{b}y) = c.$$

This implies that g is a left divisor of c .

Conversely, if g is a left divisor of c then $c = g\tilde{c}$ for some $\tilde{c} \in \mathbb{H}[d]$. By a quaternionic version of Bézout's identity [1], there exist polynomials $p, q \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ such that

$$ap + bq = g.$$

Multiplying it on the right by \tilde{c} , yields

$$a(p\tilde{c}) + b(q\tilde{c}) = g\tilde{c} = c.$$

Thus, $x = p\tilde{c}$ and $y = q\tilde{c}$ form a solution to (21). \square

Theorem 6 (General solution). Let $x', y' \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ be a particular solution of equation (21). Then, the general solution is

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x' - b_r t, \\ y &= y' + a_r t, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where $t \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ is an arbitrary quaternionic polynomial parameter, and $a_r, b_r \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ are right-coprime quaternionic polynomials satisfying

$$a^{-1}b = b_r a_r^{-1}. \quad (23)$$

Proof. Since $ax' + by' = c$, subtracting this from (21) gives the homogeneous equation

$$a(x - x') + b(y - y') = 0. \quad (24)$$

Thus, we seek all polynomial matrices $M \in \mathbb{H}^{2 \times 1}[d]$ satisfying

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b \end{bmatrix} M = 0.$$

Since $\begin{bmatrix} a & b \end{bmatrix}$ is 1×2 of rank one, M must also have rank one and can be written as

$$M = Zt$$

where Z is a full rank 2×1 matrix and $t \in \mathbb{H}[d]$ is arbitrary. Partitioning Z compatibly with $\begin{bmatrix} a & b \end{bmatrix}$, we get

$$Z = \begin{bmatrix} -b_r \\ a_r \end{bmatrix},$$

where a_r, b_r are right coprime polynomials from (23). Substituting into (24), we get

$$x - x' = -b_r t, \quad y - y' = a_r t,$$

which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 7 (Minimal solutions). If equation (21) is solvable, then among all solutions, there exists one where x has the minimum degree, satisfying

$$\deg x < \deg b_r.$$

Similarly, there exists (possibly another) solution where y has the minimum degree, satisfying

$$\deg y < \deg a_r.$$

Proof. Let x', y' be any particular solution. Performing right polynomial division on x' by \tilde{b}_r , we obtain

$$x' = b_r q + r, \quad (25)$$

where q is the quotient and r is the remainder, with $\deg r < \deg b_r$. Substituting q as the parameter t in the general solution

$$x = x' - b_r t = x' - b_r q.$$

Since (25) implies $x' - b_r q = r$, we get $x = r$, which has the minimal possible degree. The construction for minimizing $\deg y$ follows the same reasoning. \square

VII. DESIGN PROCEDURE

We use quaternionic polynomial equations to place the zeros of a closed-loop transfer function denominator in specified similarity classes. Specifically, we design an output feedback controller so that the denominator polynomial has right zeros similar to desired values—mirroring classical pole placement in a quaternionic setting.

Algorithm 2 (Design procedure).

1) Construct the desired denominator: Given the desired positions $r_i \in \mathbb{H}$, form the polynomial

$$c(d) = (d - r_1)(d - r_2) \dots \quad (26)$$

2) Compute the plant's transfer function: If a state-space model (4) is given, use Algorithm 1 to compute the left polynomial fraction

$$S = a_\ell^{-1} b_\ell = J + dH(I_n - dF)^{-1}G. \quad (27)$$

3) Solve the polynomial equation: Form the polynomial equation:

$$a_\ell p_r + b_\ell q_r = c \quad (28)$$

and solve it for unknown polynomials p_r and q_r .

4) Construct the controller transfer function:

$$R = q_r p_r^{-1} \quad (29)$$

5) Obtain the controller's state-space model: If needed, compute its realization using Theorem 2.

With this controller, the closed-loop transfer functions become

$$T_w = p_r c^{-1} a_\ell = g^{-1} h_w, \quad T_v = p_r c^{-1} b_\ell = g^{-1} h_v. \quad (30)$$

Here, c and g have right zeros similar to the prescribed r_i 's.

Unlike in classical systems, zeros cannot be placed exactly at the desired positions in \mathbb{H} , only within their similarity classes. However, this is sufficient, as all

elements in a similarity class share key properties. They are all either stable or unstable.

Example 1. Consider a plant defined by the state-space model (4) with

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{j} & \mathbf{k} \end{bmatrix}, G = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{i} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, H = [1 \ 0], J = 0.$$

The standard right eigenvalues of F are $\lambda_1 = 1.4 + 0.37\mathbf{i}, \lambda_2 = -0.37 + 1.4\mathbf{i}$ both having $|\lambda_1| = |\lambda_2| = 1.4142 > 1$ indicating instability.

Following the outlined design steps:

1) Select stable values $r_1 = 3, r_2 = 4$ in $d = z^{-1}$, forming the polynomial

$$c(d) = (d-3)(d-4) = 12 - 7d + d^2.$$

The choice of real zeros is possible but not necessary. It will have interesting consequences.

2) Using Algorithm 1, the left polynomial fraction representation of (27) gives

$$\begin{aligned} a_\ell(d) &= 1 - (1 - 0.31\mathbf{i} - 0.89\mathbf{j} - 0.35\mathbf{k})d \\ &\quad - (0.61\mathbf{i} + 1.8\mathbf{j} + 0.7\mathbf{k})d^2, \\ b_\ell(d) &= d + (0.31\mathbf{i} + 0.89\mathbf{j} + 0.35\mathbf{k})d^2. \end{aligned}$$

The right zeros of a_ℓ are computed as $z_1^{-1} = -0.37 - 0.42\mathbf{i} - 1.2\mathbf{j} - 0.48\mathbf{k}$, $z_2^{-1} = 1.4 + 0.11\mathbf{i} + 0.32\mathbf{j} + 0.13\mathbf{k}$ which are similar to the reciprocals of λ_1, λ_2 , confirming correctness.

3) Solving (28) yields

$$\begin{aligned} p_r &= 12 - (11 - 5.8\mathbf{i} - 17\mathbf{j} - 6.6\mathbf{k})d, \\ q_r(d) &= 30\mathbf{i} - 14\mathbf{j} + 10\mathbf{k} - (37\mathbf{i} - 19\mathbf{j} + 15\mathbf{k})d. \end{aligned}$$

This defines the controller transfer function $R = q_r p_r^{-1}$.

Expressing the closed-loop transfer function from w to y as a left fraction $g^{-1}h_w$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} g(d) &= 0.095 - 0.12\mathbf{i} - 0.36\mathbf{j} - 0.14\mathbf{k} \\ &\quad - (0.056 - 0.073\mathbf{i} - 0.21\mathbf{j} - 0.083\mathbf{k})d \\ &\quad + (0.008 - 0.01\mathbf{i} - 0.03\mathbf{j} - 0.012\mathbf{k})d^2, \\ h_w(d) &= 0.095 - 0.12\mathbf{i} - 0.36\mathbf{j} - 0.14\mathbf{k} \\ &\quad + (0.87 + 0.31\mathbf{i} + 0.91\mathbf{j} + 0.36\mathbf{k})d \\ &\quad - (1.9 + 0.048\mathbf{i} + 0.14\mathbf{j} + 0.055\mathbf{k})d^2 \\ &\quad + (1.1 - 0.34\mathbf{i} - 0.99\mathbf{j} - 0.39\mathbf{k})d^3. \end{aligned}$$

Despite being a quaternionic polynomial, g has real zeros 3 and 4, achieving exactly the desired placement.

The resulting closed-loop state-space model is

$$\begin{aligned} F_c &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -0.083 & 0.58 \end{bmatrix}, & G_c &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \\ H_c &= \begin{bmatrix} 3.2 + 0.56\mathbf{i} + 1.6\mathbf{j} + 0.64\mathbf{k} \\ -0.75 - 1.4\mathbf{i} - 4\mathbf{j} - 1.6\mathbf{k} \\ -1.3 + 0.79\mathbf{i} + 2.3\mathbf{j} + 0.9\mathbf{k} \end{bmatrix}^T, & J_c &= 1. \end{aligned}$$

Since $c(d)$ was chosen as real in this example, F with eigenvalues $\lambda_1(F_c) = 0.33, \lambda_2(F_c) = 0.25, \lambda_3(F_c) = 0$. As expected $\lambda_1(F_c) = 1/r_1, \lambda_2(F_c) = 1/r_2$, The third eigenvalue is zero since $c(d)$ was selected with a degree one less than the closed-loop system order.

This example shows how quaternionic polynomial equations enable pole placement in quaternion feedback systems; Figure 1 illustrates the closed-loop response.

Fig. 1. Feedback system response to a random initial state.

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